

Report: Country visit report – Lithuania

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Abbreviations table

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMR	Antimicrobial resistance
APIs	Application Programming Interfaces
ATHINA	Advanced Technology for Health INtelligence and Action IT system
CBRN	Chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear
CT	Computed Tomography
EARS-Net	European Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance Network
EC	European Commission
ECDC	European Centre of Disease and Control
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EMA	European Medicines Agency
ENSRA	European Nuclear Security Regulators Association
ENSREG	European Nuclear Safety Regulators Group
ESAC-Net	European Surveillance of Antimicrobial Consumption Network
ESARDA	European Safeguards Research and Development Association
ESPBI IS	Electronic Health Services and Cooperation Infrastructure Information System
ESVAC	European Surveillance of Veterinary Antimicrobial Consumption
ESVIS	Ekstremalių sveikatai situacijų valdymo informacinė sistema (Health emergency management IT system)
EU	European Union
EU-HIP	EU interoperability with HERA's IT platform
EURDEP	European Radiological Data Exchange Platform
EWRS	Early Warning and Response System
GP	General Practitioner
GPIS	Public Warning and Information System
HERA	EU Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority
HERCA	Heads of the European Radiological Protection Competent Authorities
HESC	Health Emergency Situations Center
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
ICD-10	International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision
ICO	Information Commissioner's Office
IH	Institute of Hygiene
IPR	Patient pre-registration system
IT	Information Technology
ITDB	Incident and Trafficking Database
LIMS	Laboratory information system
MCM(s)	Medical countermeasure(s)
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging

NCMC	National Crises Management Center
NPHSL	National Public Health Surveillance Laboratory
NPHC	National Public Health Center
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
PHPP	Pathogens with high pandemic potential
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
PPS	Point Prevalence Study
RADIS	Radiation Early Warning System
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals
RPC	Radiation Protection Center
SCIP	Substances of Concern In articles as such or in complex objects (Products)
SECR	State Enterprise Centre of Registers
SMCA	State Medicines Control Agency
SSI	Statens Serum Institute
TESSy	The European Surveillance System
THL	Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare
ULSKIS	Information system for monitoring and control of infectious diseases that can spread and pose a threat
ULSVIS	State information system of communicable diseases and their agents
USIE	Unified System for Information Exchange in Incidents and Emergencies
VMVT	State Food and Veterinary Service
WENRA	Western European Nuclear Regulators Association
WHO	World Health Organisation

INTRODUCTION

This document has been developed within the remit of the project [EU interoperability with HERA's IT platform \(EU-HIP\)](#). EU-HIP is a consortium of 15 European countries, coordinated by Statens Serum Institute (SSI), Denmark. The scope of the project is to support countries to enhance and improve national IT systems for health threats surveillance and management in an efficient and coordinated manner, with the objective of obtaining interoperability with the centralised IT platform of the EU [Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority \(HERA\)](#).

HERA's IT platform (ATHINA - Advanced Technology for Health INtelligence and Action IT system) is currently under development and seeks to gather intelligence on health threats surveillance and medical countermeasures (MCMs) to support threat assessment and crisis management across Europe. The priority areas are pathogens with high pandemic potential (PHPP), antimicrobial resistance (AMR), and Chemical, Biological, Radiological & Nuclear (CBRN) threats, as well as appropriate medical countermeasures, such as medicinal products, medical devices and personal protective equipment (PPE).

A baseline activity of the EU-HIP project is to perform a landscape assessment of countries' IT systems, in relation to the above-mentioned priorities, across all countries involved in the consortium. In addition, in-depth country visits are being performed in a small group of countries, to gain detailed insights into the functioning of such systems.

This report presents the findings from the landscape assessment and in-depth country visit in Lithuania. Such exercise has also been performed in Croatia, Denmark and Iceland.

METHODOLOGY

For the gathering of the information presented in this report, a two-step methodology has been implemented.

a. Landscape analysis

A data-gathering tool was developed by the EU-HIP partners in close collaboration with HERA, to collect background information on countries' surveillance systems, covering the topics of digital infrastructures and systems, key actors and legislative aspects. By processing the material gathered through this tool, the EU-HIP team produced an aggregated mapping of the current state of progress in national IT systems for health threats surveillance and management and medical countermeasures in Europe (Deliverable 4.1 Landscape Analysis Report).

The tool was shared and supplemented with input from several multi-disciplinary national experts. This step aimed to gather an initial understanding of the information systems, stakeholders and legislations in place across the different European countries concerning HERA's four priority topics.

b. Country visits

In the second phase, semi-structured interviews were conducted with experts, delving deeper into each topic. The goal was to gain insights into the functionality of these systems, the roles and interactions of key stakeholders and additional details about pertinent legislations. The interviews built upon the tool's pre-existing questions, encouraging experts to provide additional information beyond what had been already shared during the first main phase. The analysis of the materials collected during the country visit was shared with the country of interest for review and after approval, with HERA and made publicly available. Country-specific materials will also be used to support further work within the EU-HIP such as the identification of key areas of improvement and the actions needed to achieve interoperability with the upcoming HERA's IT platform, ATHINA.

As part of the country visit in Lithuania, nine in person interviews were performed in April 2024 over three days. An overview of the stakeholders interviewed can be found in Table 1.

Table 1. Overview of the stakeholders interviewed as part of the Lithuania country visit

Interview Date	Stakeholder
Monday 15 th April	Health Emergency Situation Centre of the Ministry of Health - Emergency prevention division
	Ministry of Health – Public Health Department
	National Public Health Surveillance Laboratory
Tuesday 16 th April	Health Emergency Situation Centre of the Ministry of Health - Medicine Stockpile Planning division
	National Public Health Center under the Ministry of Health - Division of Communicable disease management
	Radiation Protection Centre - Division of Radiation Emergency Management and Training
	Health Emergency Situation Centre of the Ministry of Health - Administration division
Wednesday 17 th April	National Public Health Center under the Ministry of Health – Division of Public Health Safety Control
	Health Emergency Situation Centre of the Ministry of Health - Medicine Reserve Storage and Pharmaceutical Activity Division

Within the EU-HIP, the Sciensano (Belgium) and Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) teams were responsible for conducting the interviews and writing the final report. The country visit was organised with the support of the Lithuanian Health Emergency Situation Centre of the Ministry of Health for the identification of the stakeholders, planning of interviews and provision of additional explanation when needed. During the interviews, the assessors took notes that were summarised afterwards in the form of a report. The interviews were recorded for minutes purposes.

RESULTS

I. Pathogens with high pandemic potential

a. Key actors and stakeholder networks

In Lithuania, the [Ministry of Health](#) formulates and implements national health policies, coordinates resources and provides guidelines. It works closely with various health stakeholders to adapt strategies and responses to the evolving situations posed by health threats. The Ministry of Health in Lithuania comprises five departments: Public Health, Health Care, Pharmaceutical, Strategic, and Investment. Within the Public Health Department, there are two divisions: Public Health Safety and Health Promotion. These divisions are also tasked with ensuring preparedness for health threats and emergency situations. The Ministry of Health actively participates in national and international activities such as the European Centre of Disease and Control (ECDC) management board committee, HERA board, Council of Ministers and the Health Security Committee of the European Commission. In response to evolving challenges, the department has increased its capacity for addressing health emergencies. At the national level, the Public Health department is responsible for guiding the strategy for the next three years. The Ministry of Health has strong connections with the Ministry of Interior and the Fire and Rescue Department, involving these entities in preparedness planning, including stockpiling and logistics. The Ministry of Health is responsible for the implementation of the [Government plan 2023-2027 for digitalization of health systems](#), covering all the health sector and aiming to digitalise all health records.

The aim of the [National Public Health Center \(NPHC\)](#) under the Ministry of Health is to protect public health by managing risks related to infectious diseases, environmental factors, services and products provided to consumers. The NPHC conducts infectious diseases epidemiological surveillance and collects and analyses data on the spread of these diseases and threats. It provides scientific guidance, develops guidelines and support coordination of public health threats. The NPHC is also involved in PHPP related to **One Health** activities, including multiple EU projects, and collaborates closely with the [State Veterinary and Food Safety Service](#) on these initiatives. The cooperation for exchanging information is formalized through a Ministry of Health order.

The [National Public Health Surveillance Laboratory \(NPHSL\)](#), now subsidiary of NPHC, is responsible for AMR, biological threats and highly infectious pathogen testing. During the pandemic, it conducted testing for both COVID-19 and influenza, contributing to the identification and confirmation of cases.

The [Health Emergency Situations Center \(HESC\)](#) of the Ministry of Health aims to protect public health by ensuring the readiness of the healthcare system for emergency situations. HESC participates in legislative processes, developing and administering the state medical reserve to ensure adequate MCM during crises. It organizes training and exercises for emergency preparedness, and it engages in national and international projects to enhance emergency health management, representing Lithuania in various international forums.

The [National Crisis Management Centre \(NCMC\)](#) under the Government of Lithuania is responsible for the management of national-level crises and emergencies. The Center includes a situation center that operates 24/7, continuously monitoring threats to national security. Its

primary responsibilities include coordinating with relevant stakeholders during crises, supporting prevention of threats and overseeing communication related to national security.

The [Institute of Hygiene \(IH\)](#) carries out state functions in different public health areas. Its mission is to monitor the health status of Lithuanian residents and the activities of healthcare institutions, assessing public health inequalities and public healthcare technologies, researching the effects of the work environment on health, strengthening mental health, health education and disease prevention, and developing the competencies of healthcare and pharmaceutical specialists.

The [State Data Agency](#) (also referred to as Statistics Lithuania) is a government institution responsible for shaping and implementing state policy in official statistics and data governance under the Ministries of Finance and, Economy and Innovation. It coordinates the production of official statistics and manages data processing according to the [Official Statistics and State Data Governance Law](#). The Agency oversees the [Official Statistics Portal](#), ensuring compliance with national and EU regulations. Its functions include preparing and submitting statistical programs and reports, conducting and evaluating statistical surveys and publish datasets for reuse on the [Lithuanian Open Data Portal](#). The State Data Agency will be the competent body for health data for the European Health Data Space (EHDS).

The [State Enterprise Centre of Registers \(SECR\)](#) is a public entity of limited civil liability incorporated by the Government of the Republic of Lithuania. It hosts more than 60 registries, covering different sectors and providing access for a fee to the data. The regulations for accessing the data are currently under review in the country.

A network of public health institutions within municipalities, known as **Public Health Bureaus**, is tasked with two primary functions: promoting health within the municipality and providing healthcare services in schools and kindergartens. These programs focus on preventive measures tailored specifically for children. During emergencies such as the COVID-19 pandemic, these bureaus played a crucial role in organizing testing and tracking of new cases within schools. In the event of a confirmed case, thorough contact tracing was conducted, and pertinent information was relayed to the NPHC, which oversaw the overall epidemiological surveillance of COVID-19 cases.

b. Digital infrastructures and systems

i. Data sources and systems

The National Public Health Center manages two information systems for the identification and assessment of health threats from infectious diseases:

- **State information system of communicable diseases and their agents** (*Užkrečiamųjų ligų ir jų sukėlėjų valstybės informacinė Sistema - ULSVIS*): Notification of a case (list of notifiable diseases available in Annex 1) is received by the NPHC from hospitals through a paper-based 058 form ([Formą Nr. 058-089-151/a „Pranešimas apie nustatytą \(įtariamą\) susirgimą](#)) or from general practitioners (GP) through the Electronic Health Services and Cooperation Infrastructure Information System (ESPBI IS). Paper-based information is entered by NPHC in the ULSVIS system whereas the ESPBI IS platform has interoperability with the ULSVIS system since the beginning of 2024. Future plans include integrating hospital 058 forms into the ESPBI IS for a more

streamlined process. All the information (including personal identification number for linkage of data) to be shared during the notification of a case is specified in [Order Nr. 673](#). Infectious diseases in ULSVIS are filled in accordance to [Order Nr. V-414](#) "On the approval of forms of epidemiological diagnostic protocols for cases of identified infectious diseases and specific health problems".

- **State Tuberculosis Information System:** hosted in Santaros Klinikos, Vilnius University Hospital, it has recently been moved to the NPHC after an audit of information systems conducted by the Ministry of Health. Data and analysis for tuberculosis continues to be conducted in Santaros Klinikos. Santaros Klinikos is the data processor of the State Tuberculosis Information System and NPHC is the manager of the State Tuberculosis Information System. During the second phase of ULSVIS modernization, which is currently underway, the State Tuberculosis Information System will be integrated into ULSVIS, making ULSVIS the only information system for all communicable diseases.

The **Information system for monitoring and control of infectious diseases that can spread and pose a threat** (*Užkrečiamųjų ligų, galinčių išplisti ir kelti grėsmę, stebėsenos ir kontrolės informacinė sistema - ULSKIS*) was established specifically for COVID-19 ([Order "No. V-438"](#)) as the ULSVIS system did not have sufficient capacity to manage COVID-19 related information, including information regarding isolated people as well as passenger locator forms. This system was used for verifying information on COVID-19 cases, managing epidemiological diagnostics and coordinating data reporting. However, from July 1, 2024, this information system has been liquidated and its functionality transferred to ULSVIS.

Plans are underway to redevelop and strengthen the infectious disease data management system. As a lesson from COVID-19 pandemic management, the elements in the ULSKIS system related to emergency management have been integrated in the upgraded ULSVIS system. The Ministry of Health is responsible for these efforts, particularly through its Public Health department, which oversees digitalization. The objective is to merge the three mentioned systems into one unified system by 2027, funded by the European Structural Funds. This funding ensures that the development can proceed without financial constraints, aiming to create a robust, scalable and unified system capable of handling large volumes of data and managing future health emergencies effectively. Improvements are also ongoing regarding the NPHSL, hospital and private healthcare institution laboratories to enter data directly in ULSVIS.

The **Electronic information system of health services and cooperation infrastructure (ESPBI IS)** (also referred to as eHealth) aims to centrally collect, store and administer information related to health services provided in Lithuania. It collects both medical and administrative information related to healthcare providers and recipients. It facilitates the registration of e-health services provided to patients and allows access to information about services that have already been rendered. This comprehensive system ensures that healthcare data is systematically recorded and accessible, improving the efficiency and quality of healthcare delivery. However, certain types of data are stored locally in hospitals due to the large storage requirements. Scans like X-rays, which are smaller in file size (up to 5 MB), are more readily available. Larger files, such as MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging) and CT (Computed Tomography) scans, may not be immediately accessible due to size and system limitations. These larger files often need to be manually uploaded upon request or transferred physically via USB or CD if the patient visits other healthcare providers. One of the primary

challenges is the time required to retrieve and upload large scans, which can take between 30 minutes to an hour due to limited bandwidth and server capacity, especially during peak usage times. Additionally, hospital information systems are not directly interconnected, leading to delays in data transfer between systems. In this regard, a priority for the future is to improve high-speed throughput within the systems. This involves reducing the time patients and doctors spend interacting with the system by ensuring faster data retrieval and upload. Efforts are being made to enhance server capacities and upgrade network infrastructure to handle high data volumes more efficiently. As part of Lithuania's four-year digitalization plan (2023–2027), efforts will also focus on improving the user-friendliness of the eHealth platform as both healthcare professionals and patients have expressed difficulties in finding and retrieving some personal information in the system.

The [Patient pre-registration system \(IPR\)](#) is an integral part of ESPBI and allows both patients and health personnel to schedule medical appointments. This is done remotely and is faster than other existing means, such as by phone call or visiting a healthcare facility. IPR allows patients to remotely find all registrations in one place with doctors, book an appointment, receive notifications and reminders about scheduled visits to the doctor, cancel a doctor's appointment and monitor the history of all planned and completed visits. IPR helps to create an even distribution of patients between medical institutions and specialists, and patients can see what the real availability of doctors is and can choose the facility where it will be possible to get to the doctor faster.

The [Hygiene Institute](#) oversees health data analysis and all related registries. These registries encompass a wide range of statistics, including but not limited to mortality rates, children's health, injuries and organ donors. Whenever the Ministry of Health requires data analysis, they engage with the institute to procure the necessary data.

The country has a publicly available [COVID-19 Portal](#). It provides COVID-19 dashboards and statistical data related to the pandemic in Lithuania. It offers comprehensive visualizations and up-to-date information on infection rates, testing, vaccinations and other key metrics. The dashboards help track the impact of COVID-19 across different regions of Lithuania, aiding both policymakers and the public in understanding and responding to the health crisis effectively. The data to the COVID-19 dashboard flows directly from the eHealth system.

Vaccination records of residents of Lithuania are also available in the eHealth platform and accessible by the NPHC. Currently some data in regard to vaccination is publicly shared in a pdf format. According to the government plan ([Order Nr. DJ-21](#) and implementation [Order Nr. 849](#)), health institutions are required to make more data available in an open format. In that perspective, NPHC is working to make their data on vaccine preventable diseases available to the public.

ii. [Data linkage and sharing](#)

Lithuania has a national personal identification number, which is called the "Asmens kodas" or "Personal code" issued by the State Enterprise Centre of Registers (SECR). This Centre is responsible for maintaining the population register and issuing personal identification numbers to citizens and residents of Lithuania. This unique identifier is assigned to each citizen or resident of Lithuania and is used for various administrative purposes, including healthcare, taxation and social security. It is commonly used for healthcare purposes that allows healthcare providers to access patient records, track medical history and manage healthcare services for

individuals within the healthcare system. This integration of the personal code into healthcare systems helps ensure accurate record-keeping and efficient delivery of healthcare services to residents of Lithuania. In addition to the personal code, the eHealth system uses also a “patient identifier code” as not every patient may have a personal code (e.g. non-residents).

Lithuania has 60 municipalities and 58 regional offices. However, some municipalities, especially smaller ones, do not have infectious disease specialists on site. These municipalities can have access to infectious disease data, but there is no personnel that monitors it. Consequently, the monitoring of infectious disease data is managed at the regional level. This ensures that no critical information is overlooked and that any local outbreaks can be managed effectively by local authorities, rather than waiting for directives from larger cities like Vilnius.

Legislation mandates that all health institutions, regardless of being public or private, provide aggregated data on infectious diseases. This ensures that public health authorities have a comprehensive view of disease prevalence, essential for effective public health management. Lithuania submits individual personalized data on infectious diseases to the [European Surveillance System \(TESSy\)](#) in accordance with the annual data submission schedule established by the ECDC. The NPHC aims to monitor and coordinate public health responses across the EU, facilitating the exchange of data on epidemiological information for timely and coordinated action during extreme health problems such as pandemics. In addition to TESSy, Lithuania also participates in the [Early Warning and Response System \(EWRS\)](#) for other public health preparedness and response issues, with NPHC as the responsible stakeholder. EWRS allows rapid communication and coordination between EU countries on various public health threats beyond COVID-19 and influenza but also other infectious diseases, ensuring a unified approach to managing and mitigating health risks across Europe. International information exchange is not automated but conducted manually.

iii. Data storage

The Institute of Hygiene hosts public health data, epidemiological data and data from health surveys while the SECR houses registers from various domains, including health and employment. The State Data Agency, which is the principal data agency, provides access to the data. Researchers must submit research proposals to access data, usually to the State Data Agency or directly to the relevant institute (data owner). An ethical committee evaluates these proposals, with two regional ethical committees based in major universities and a national committee located in Vilnius. Researchers must obtain a permit from either the regional or national committee, which is then submitted with their application to the governing body responsible for data access. The application process requires a detailed explanation of the data's intended use, including a two-page research plan. A data management plan must outline how the data will be managed, stored and used safely. The application review takes approximately 14 days, with data access granted within two days thereafter.

Data collection in the SECR has been electronic for the past decade, with full implementation since 2019. The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated data collection efforts, resulting in 100% electronic issuance of death and birth certificates. Researchers can request data linkage from multiple registries, though this incurs additional fees.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the NPHC managed COVID-19 data due to its capacity for data storage and administrative handling. However, the analysis and access provision were handled by the State Data Agency.

iv. Standards and data quality

Standardised templates and forms are used for all pathogens. The International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision (ICD-10) is widely implemented in the country.

Currently, the NPHC lacks a publicly accessible metadata catalogue. This absence means that crucial information about the data holdings, such as details regarding the types, sources and structures of datasets, is not readily available to the public or other stakeholders.

v. Reports

The NPHC published monthly reports on [their website](#) on morbidity in communicable diseases and vaccination. A dashboard on vaccination is being planned while one on [COVID-19 and influenza data](#) is already available.

At the onset of each year, every health institute writes an annual work plan, which is then submitted to the Ministry of Health for evaluation. The Ministry of Health then collaborates with various departments to review these plans in accordance with their respective areas of expertise and provide suggestions for improvements.

vi. Threat indicators

Detection is defined by the screening process of analysing specific datasets/data elements (e.g. a public health signal, threat or event detected by a software) to check if these datasets/data elements meet a certain criterion, pre-defined for the selection for further analysis.

- Public health signal for COVID-19 and influenza;
- Threat (one case) for Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever, Ebola and Marburg virus diseases, and Lassa fever, poliomyelitis caused by wild strain poliovirus, influenza caused by a new subtype of the virus, SARS.

Threat detection, assessment and validation requires the involvement of one or more experts. The information system gives an automated notification if for COVID-19 or influenza a certain threshold has been reached. Consequently, NPHC contacts the authorities at the county level to inform them and to evaluate together what type of measures need to be taken.

Additionally, the National Crisis Management Center, operates a situation center on a 24/7 basis for the management of crises and emergencies. Staffed by representatives from various agencies such as the National Ambulance Center, State Border Control, military, police, and Fire and Rescue Department, this Center monitors events using a range of analytical tools. These tools include visual aids, signal capture and analytical data sourced from diverse channels, enabling comprehensive situational awareness and informed decision-making. In the event of a crisis or emergency, the NCMC will coordinate efforts to prevent national security threats, oversee the actions of state reserve managers and handle strategic communication related to national security.

c. Legislation and strategy

The Minister of Health issued [Order “No. 278” regarding the list of dangerous and particularly dangerous infectious diseases](#) (Annex 1), for which patients, suspected cases, contacts or carriers of the causative agents of these diseases must be hospitalized, isolated, tested and treated compulsorily. The Order was updated in 2022 and it includes amendments to the preamble and specifies procedures for hospitalization, isolation, testing and treatment in healthcare facilities under specific circumstances.

The [Ministerial Decree "No. 673"](#), issued in 2022 and last updated in 2023, provides information regarding mandatory epidemiological registration, the content of mandatory information about objects of epidemiological registration and the procedure for mandatory information transmission. It outlines the procedures and responsibilities regarding the registration and reporting of infectious diseases, carriers of infectious diseases, incidences of infectious diseases and deaths resulting from these diseases. The decree specifies the obligations of healthcare institutions and personnel in registering, reporting and maintaining records of individuals affected by infectious diseases. It also covers the reporting procedures for specific diseases such as tuberculosis, sexually transmitted diseases and others. Additionally, it addresses the responsibilities during outbreaks of infectious diseases and the compilation of monthly reports summarizing registered cases. Amendments to the regulation were made in November 2023 to align with the Law on the Prevention and Control of Infectious Diseases of the Republic of Lithuania and Regulation (EU) 2022/2371 of the European Parliament and of the Council, to adapt the description of the procedure for the registration of mandatory epidemiological cases and the provision of information about them and reporting requirements for different categories of healthcare professionals.

A new law is consolidating all emergency situation-related acts into one document. This law will specify supervision, frequency of review, recommendations, and it will include private healthcare institutions in preparedness efforts. Previously, only the national healthcare system was responsible for testing, vaccination and other critical activities, leading to dissatisfaction as many people transitioned to private care. The amended legislation now mandates that private institutions also maintain PPE, participate in all emergency activities and have preparedness plans. Recommendations from reviews will be binding, requiring institutions to make necessary changes and resubmit plans for approval. To accommodate different sizes and types of healthcare providers, a simplified plan will be created for smaller private institutions and GP teams, while larger hospitals will have more detailed requirements.

Regarding Artificial Intelligence (AI) in health and preparedness, there is currently no law regulating its use in the country.

i. Emergency plans

As the COVID-19 pandemic emerged, the Ministry of Health initially lacked specific emergency plans. However, established procedures were in place for activating the Emergency Operation Center, an ad hoc body established in the presence of a crisis with the Minister of Health at its head. This Center served as the central command for coordinating the national response. Throughout the two-year crisis, daily meetings were held to address evolving challenges, relying on established protocols to mobilize resources and engage stakeholders. Updated

procedures are now established under newly enacted law on [Crisis Management and Civil Protection](#).

During COVID-19, the communication division at the Ministry collaborated with the ECDC communication team for recommendations. However, there is no separate plan for communication in time of crises. During COVID-19, communication was handled twice a day, with a specialist preparing the minister on current news and expected questions. The NPHC utilized social media platforms like Facebook and LinkedIn for dissemination. Post-COVID, there is no specific communication plan in place. However, there is a National Health Fund, supported by three million euros from alcohol taxes, half of which is allocated for communication activities each year. A council decides the priorities for this fund, and a significant portion is dedicated to health improvement and vaccination communication efforts. This fund ensures ongoing support for public health communication activities.

During the post-COVID-19 crisis period, Lithuania undertook an evaluation of its pandemic response to identify strengths and areas for improvement specific to their contact tracing system. Subsequently, an action review for COVID-19 case management and contact tracing was conducted in collaboration with ECDC and in agreement between the NPHC and the Ministry of Health. However, there are no specific plans for systematic evaluation of how a crisis is handled as part of the pandemic preparedness plan.

By law, healthcare institutions must have emergency plans, a sample of which is reviewed by HESC. Institutions submit their plans covering, among others, training, countermeasures and contact information for responsible personnel and legal acts, which are reviewed for compliance using a questionnaire. If a plan scores low, it is checked more frequently. The information provided as part of the emergency plans will be extended and will be requested by both public and private sector institutions, significantly increasing the number of plans to be reviewed (from 250 up to 4000).

A new health emergencies management IT system (Ekstremalių sveikatai situacijų valdymo informacinė sistema - ESVIS) is currently under development which aims to digitalize these paper plans and implement automated checks for completeness and ensuring all obligatory information is included before submission. This system will enhance communication efficiency, allowing for direct messaging and email exchange, thereby transitioning from a paper-based to a digital system. The system, with specifications completed last year, is expected to be operational by 2025, providing an efficient way to check and monitor emergency preparedness across institutions. It will also track the training certifications of those responsible for emergency preparedness.

Although some supervision is conducted at hospitals and outpatient clinics, comprehensive checks are not feasible without an automated system. Annually, a plan is drafted to outline the number of institutions scheduled for inspection. For the current year, 48 institutions have been preselected for review. The implementation of the ESVIS system is expected to increase the capacity for inspections. The 14 main hospitals, identified as critical for emergency response, are prioritized in the selection process.

Additionally, the hospital safety index (tool used to assess the safety and preparedness of hospitals to function effectively during and after emergencies) is being incorporated into the emergency plans. This index, now translated into the local language, is integrated into the ESVIS system in the form of additional questions. Healthcare facilities will complete this

questionnaire to obtain a safety score, with training provided on how to fill the questionnaire effectively. This component will form a critical part of the emergency situation plan.

ii. Action plans

A diverse array of strengthening programs is implemented across the country, with institutions actively participating in specific projects and actions. European funds play a significant role in funding these initiatives, with two distinct programs - one focusing on public health ([No. 11-001-02-10-03-\(RE\)](#)) and the other on healthcare ([Nr. 11-002-02-11-01](#)). Within the public health program, there are two action plans: one addressing public health concerns, and another dedicated to mental health. These programs encompass a wide range of activities aimed at increasing preparedness against health threats, with the involvement of various institutions including laboratories, the NPHC, the Radiation Protection Center and the Hygiene Institute. The Ministry assumes responsibility for ensuring the competence of specialists involved in these initiatives. Separate action plans have been developed for immunization, tuberculosis, HIV and sexually transmitted diseases, each spanning three to five years. The National Expert Committee for Immunization collaborates with HERA on procurement suggestions, such as vaccines for avian influenza and monkeypox.

Further strengthening plans foresees the establishment of new infectious disease departments in five major hospitals. These departments will be equipped to handle future pandemics, featuring specialized labs capable of performing tests and sequencing. The NPHSL will support these hospitals, ensuring robust testing capabilities. The development plan also includes budget allocations for equipment, staff training and materials necessary for these enhanced laboratory services.

iii. Training

Multiple activities are currently ongoing related to training:

- Training program for public health specialists with a budget of four million euros allocated until 2027. The Hygiene Institute is responsible for this initiative, and discussions are ongoing to identify the target groups of specialists and the essential training topics.
- Special initiative focusing on health literacy development, also funded with four million euros over the next five years. This initiative aims to improve health literacy at the population level, with a particular focus on vulnerable groups, such as children, individuals aged 65 and above and those with chronic diseases or cancer. A significant part of this effort is dedicated to emergency preparedness, ensuring that these vulnerable populations are better equipped to handle health emergencies.
- Specific training programs for public health employees to update their knowledge, which are conducted with emergency medical teams as part of a broader training efforts.
- A working group is integrating war medicine and crisis management into the curricula for medical and nursing students. The Ministry of Interior is also developing a civil

protection plan that includes hospital preparedness, communication equipment, and other essential resources.

- A national training system is being formulated by HESC to ensure that personnel are adequately prepared for emergency situations. The Hygiene Institute, which houses the competence center, will oversee these training programs.
- Discussions are currently ongoing on whether a pandemic preparedness certificate should also be designed for healthcare personnel which would need to be renewed every few years by them to ensure continuous update of their knowledge on the subject. Experts are being sought through a tender process to develop the necessary training programs and materials. Due to financial constraints, collaboration with universities is being considered as a potential solution to leverage existing resources.
- Development of an emergency medical team certified by the WHO. This team, consisting of 60 doctors and nurses, will be prepared to assist other countries during emergencies. Training is provided by the WHO, but the certification process is managed by the National Ambulance Service. The primary activities include training and equipping the team to be self-sufficient for two weeks when deployed internationally. This autumn, certification will commence, with the process expected to take about one year.

II. Antimicrobial resistance

a. Key actors and stakeholder networks

The [Ministry of Health](#) is responsible for national coordination and policy making related to antimicrobial resistance (AMR). For national coordination on AMR, the [Ministerial Order on the approval of the inventory of procedures for the management of antimicrobial resistance in counties](#) in 2015 established an Antimicrobial Resistance Management Group. According to the Ministerial Order, the members of the group include the National Centre for Public Health, territorial health insurance funds, municipal public health offices, personal healthcare institutions, the National Public Health Surveillance Laboratory, higher education institutions, the departments of the State Food and Veterinary Service, the Department of Environmental Protection under the Ministry of Environment and other interested institutions whose activities are related to the management of AMR, representatives and municipal doctors. Methodological assistance for the Group's activities is provided by the Institute of Hygiene which also serves as the coordinating body at national level for the Group and provides related training. Additionally, there is an informal working group between various ministries and including a representative from National Public Health Surveillance Laboratory (NPHSL), meeting approximately twice a year. Representatives from Finland and Sweden have taken part in this work.

A One Health approach has been initiated between various ministries and recently (in March 2024) discussions have started regarding collaboration between broader range of stakeholders beyond only medical and veterinary authorities, including plant and environmental related issues. The Ministry of Health is expected to lead this process which is informal for the time being.

The [Institute of Hygiene \(IH\)](#), in addition to coordinating the Antimicrobial Resistance Management Group, is responsible for collecting data on antimicrobial consumption and has focal points for AMR survey, collecting information directly from the hospitals. It is also responsible for collecting hospital infections related information, including reporting thereof to the ECDC. During the country visit no interviews were conducted with the IH which poses a limitation to this report.

The [National Public Health Center](#) hosts the [NPHSL](#) which is a reference laboratory for [eight resistant antimicrobials](#) as defined by the Ministry of Health. The NPHSL has reference strains in the laboratory. NPHSL is responsible for sequencing and communicating with hospitals for the prevention of outbreaks. This started in 2019 and has increased significantly during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. NPHSL is responsible for reporting to the World Health Organisation (WHO), and the ECDC receives the information from them. The report is uploaded following the [ECDC reporting protocol](#).

There are 17 laboratories in Lithuania however, their testing capacity varies. With regard to management and investigation of hospital infections, the IH is responsible for the investigation and survey with the infection control department of the hospital in question, for reference and for laboratory investigation for clusters. However, there is no actor responsible for coordination and information sharing between the hospitals concerned.

The [State Medicines Control Agency](#) monitors the prescriptions issued and the amount of antibiotics sold and reports the data annually to the IH, which in turn is responsible for reporting to the ECDC.

The [State Food and Veterinary Service \(VMVT\)](#) carries out state food and veterinary control, supervision and control of breeding of farm animals and is responsible for veterinary pharmacy. VMVT collects data on antimicrobial consumption in animals and is responsible for reporting to the European Medicines Agency (EMA) and other international bodies. This includes monitoring trends in antimicrobial use and identifying areas where overuse or misuse occurs.

The [National Food and Veterinary Risk Assessment Institute](#) is the designated risk assessment institution in Lithuania providing scientific and technical assistance in the field of food safety and veterinary, as well performing functions of the national reference laboratory and carrying out laboratory tests in the areas of food and feed safety, quality and animal health.

b. Digital infrastructures and systems

i. Data sources and systems

Generally, the digitalization of AMR information management is required across the human, veterinary and environmental sectors. So far, no plans of integration of data of AMR circulating subtypes are foreseen. Both national reference laboratories - veterinary and public health - are able to sequence AMR-related pathogens (e. g. E. coli), but no reports or information are shared among veterinary and public health sectors.

The ULSVIS infectious diseases management system includes an AMR sub-system. In 2023, the NPHSL collected 2,000 resistant strains using paper-based information exchange. Microbiology laboratories submit data via email, using [forms available on the NPHSL website](#), within 72 hours of completing investigations. The antimicrobial sensitivity results of identified bacteria are stored in the NPHSL's internal database. Currently, sensitivity data is reported only as positive, unclear or negative, without numerical values. However, reporting on sensitivity numbers would be beneficial for obtaining comprehensive picture of AMR and for preventing outbreaks. Capacity of laboratories emerged as one of the challenges regarding AMR control and prevention. Not all laboratories in Lithuania have the necessary expertise to conduct AMR-related testing and therefore, tests are also received from Latvia.

AMR related data collection at the national level is the primary responsibility of the IH. It is responsible for collecting data on hospital infections as well as antimicrobial consumption. They collect this information digitally directly from the hospitals as well as from the State Medicines Control Agency from which they receive data on outpatient antibiotic consumption. IH also collects information about pharmaceutical consumption in hospitals. Real-time follow up is possible as each hospital has an infection control department. Hospitals are coded and reported to ECDC. From NPHSL point of view, there is a gap in information collection between the hospitals in case of a cluster outbreak. Effective management and control of hospital infection outbreaks between hospitals and communities require better coordination. Currently, the NPHC does not participate in investigating hospital infections.

IH also compares the antimicrobial consumption in the veterinary sector, working in collaboration with the VMVT. According to the AMR Action Plan, the role of VMVT is to monitor zoonotic and symbiotic bacteria and strengthen market and accounting control of veterinary

medicinal products. VMVT works with professional associations in the sector on the responsible use of antimicrobials and aims to support evidence-based practices and professional development and increase public awareness.

For IH, the main source of information on various aspects on AMR is a point prevalence study (PPS). The healthcare institutions that have active beds are required to execute PPS. Continuous surveillance usually is not done extensively in the active treatment hospitals, and they rely on the PPS, especially in hospitals which do not perform surgeries.

Regarding primary healthcare, the percentage of narrow spectrum antibiotics out of all antibiotics is being monitored and there are national indicators and a financial incentive for primary healthcare actors to use narrow spectrum antibiotics instead of broad-spectrum antibiotics. However, the size and demographics of the patients in different regions differ making it difficult to compare the primary healthcare institutions' actual performance in this regard. The Ministry of Health has plans to revise the indicators in the future.

According to the interviews conducted, there is a difference between prescriptions and the actual consumption of antibiotics and the hesitancy of taking antibiotics is somewhat high in the country.

AI solutions are not currently used in AMR surveillance in Lithuania.

ii. Data linkage and sharing

Each clinical laboratory has a laboratory information system (LIMS), or a laboratory registration form (journal). Currently, most (80%) of the laboratories already have a digital LIMS in place. For human samples, unique ID is generated that can be traced back to the patient in the hospital (in case of hospitalization) through the integrations of LIMS and hospital information system.

On antibiotic consumption in hospital, hospitals submit their data to the IH annually while performing monitoring based on [European Surveillance of Antimicrobial Consumption Network \(ESAC-Net\) methodology](#).

Data on AMR is shared internationally to the ECDC (TESSy) and WHO Global Antimicrobial Resistance and Use Surveillance System (GLASS). NPHSL and HI take part in the [European Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance Network \(EARS-Net\)](#), and HI participates in the ESAC-Net of ECDC.

NPHSL sends reference strains to WHO, and sequencing is conducted if needed for outbreaks.

iii. Data storage

There is national IT infrastructure in place for storage and processing of all AMR data in Lithuania, based on hospital and laboratory information systems and an AMR sub-system in the ULSVIS infectious diseases management system. However, there is no secure cloud specifically for AMR related healthcare data.

iv. Standards and data quality

There is an internal metadata catalogue available for AMR data in NPHSL, using ArcGIS and Palantir.

ICD-10 is used as a standard.

v. Reports

As a reference laboratory, the NPHSL presents the data about AMR annually by 1 April to the IH, the Infectious Diseases and AIDS Center and on [NPHSL website](#), as described in the Ministerial Order V-1194 of 2013.

As established in the Ministerial Order V-322 of 2015, the IH publishes [annual activity reports](#) on the activities of the Antimicrobe Resistance Management Group.

Part of the data is published in open format on [the government open data portal](#), including [report on the use of antimicrobial drugs in Lithuania](#); [antimicrobial resistance monitoring](#); [report on the use of antimicrobial drugs in Lithuania](#); [Public health impact assessment reports](#) are available on the NPHSL website.

vi. Threat indicators

Threat detection for AMR is event-based. Threat detection and validation is not automated, it involves manual analysis by experts. Validated threats are reported internationally to EARS-Net by both NPHSL and IH.

a. Legislation and strategy

The [Law on the Prevention and Control of Communicable Diseases in Humans](#) outlines the mandatory reporting of specific communicable diseases, including drug-resistant infections, by healthcare providers. Laboratories are obligated to report cases of AMR when detected. It is important to highlight that according to the current legislation, only resistant strains are required to be sent to the national reference laboratory. To prevent outbreaks, it would be useful to also see data on intermediate-resistant strains.

The [Ministerial Order on the approval of the description of the procedure for monitoring the resistance of clinically and epidemiologically important microorganisms to antimicrobial drugs and the collection, accumulation, analysis and presentation of data on the resistance of microorganisms to antimicrobial drugs](#) (Order V-1194 of 18 December 2013) regulates the monitoring of resistance at the national level and establish the procedure for identification of clinically and epidemiologically important bacteria which are listed in the Annex 1 of the Order. According to the Order, the monitoring of the resistance is coordinated at the national level by the NPHSL. All microbiology laboratories are mandated by the Order to monitor the resistance of micro-organisms and submit the data to NPHSL.

The [Ministerial Order on the approval of the description of the procedure for monitoring the use of antimicrobial medicinal products](#) (Order V-228 of 19 February 2015) regulates the monitoring of the use of antimicrobial medicinal products i.a. in order to be able to monitor consumption trends and inequalities in the country and in the personal healthcare institutions, and to provide aggregated country data to ECDC's [European Surveillance of Antimicrobial Consumption Network \(ESAC-Net\)](#).

The [Ministerial Order on the approval of the inventory of procedures for the management of antimicrobial resistance in counties](#) (Order V-322 of 5 March 2015) describes procedures for the management of AMR in counties. The objective is to monitor and manage the use of

antimicrobial medicinal products as well as to promote proper administration and use of antimicrobial medicinal products based on research and good practice, ensuring the implementation of the recommendations of the WHO and the European Union at local level. To ensure the effective implementation, the Ministerial Order established an Antimicrobial Resistance Management Group.

The [Ministerial Order on the approval of the 2017-2021 action plan for the prevention and control of the spread of antimicrobial-resistant microorganisms](#) (Order V-857 of 7 July 2017) approved the national AMR action plan 2017-2021, and the said plan is presented as an annex in the Ministerial Order. The action plan aimed to mitigate the growing threat of AMR in Lithuania by enhancing cooperation between human, veterinary and environmental sectors, improving monitoring, promoting responsible drug use, and increasing awareness. One of the challenges identified in the action plan is that the medical and veterinary sectors work separately – data on AMR and antimicrobial drug consumption are collected in the veterinary and human medical sectors using different data formats and protocols, making data comparisons difficult. The [Ministerial Order on the Prevention and Control of the Spread of Antimicrobial-Resistant Microorganisms and Hospital Infections Approval of the 2023 – 2027 Action Plan](#) approved the latest action plan with the inclusion of hospital acquired infections, for the years 2023-2027, with the objective to develop cross-sectoral cooperation in the management of AMR and the implementation of the One Health principle; expand and improve systems for monitoring antimicrobial resistance, antimicrobial use and nosocomial infections; improve the use of antimicrobial medicinal products in medicine through the introduction of scientific evidence-based tools and examples of good practice; reduce inequalities in the management of nosocomial infections through evidence-based infection prevention and control measures; raise public awareness and understanding of AMR; and conduct research on the use of antimicrobial medicinal products and AMR, the search for and evaluation of effective measures to reduce the consumption of antimicrobial medicinal products and antimicrobial resistance.

In 2023, the Ministry of Health also approved the [National Recommendations for the Rational Use of Antimicrobial Medicinal Products](#), which are guidelines for the empiric treatment of infections intended for medical specialists who prescribe antimicrobial medicinal products in their practice. The main objectives of the recommendations are to ensure appropriate empiric treatment of infectious diseases with antimicrobial medicinal products; avoid the use of certain antimicrobial medicinal products without clear clinical indications; and to reduce the risks of emergence of resistant microorganisms.

Regarding international actions, the [European Parliament resolution of 1 June 2023 on EU action to combat antimicrobial resistance](#) includes provisions on national action plans against AMR; surveillance and monitoring of AMR and antimicrobial consumption; infection prevention and control, and water, sanitation and hygiene; antimicrobial stewardship and prudent use of antimicrobials; recommended targets for antimicrobial consumption and AMR in Member States by 2030; awareness, education and training; research and development and incentives for innovation and access to antimicrobials and other AMR medical countermeasures; cooperation; and global action. In Lithuania, the Institute of Hygiene is responsible for incorporating relevant EU regulatory framework into national legislation.

Furthermore, as part of [the European Surveillance of Veterinary Antimicrobial Consumption \(ESVAC\)](#) project, from January 2024, all EU/EEA Member States must report their data on the volume of sales and use of antimicrobial medicinal products in animals, in line with the

[Veterinary Medicinal Products Regulation](#). EU/EEA Member States must use the EMA's [Antimicrobial Sales and Use Platform](#) to report their data to EMA.

[The Director of the State Food and Veterinary Service of the Republic of Lithuania Order \(Order No. B1-201 of 12 March 2004\) On the Approval of Veterinary Drug Trade and Accounting Rules](#), was replaced in 2023 with the [Order on the Approval of the Description of the Procedure for Registration, Suspension of Registration, Revocation of Suspension and Revocation of Registration of Veterinary Drugs](#) (Order No. B1-132). The Order outlines the procedures for the registration, suspension, and cancellation of registration of veterinary medicinal products in Lithuania. The procedure for registering, suspending, and canceling the registration of veterinary medicines is formalized. This regulation ensures the proper oversight and control of veterinary medicines, with specific procedures for handling registrations, maintaining compliance with safety standards, and addressing any issues that arise post-registration.

The VMVT has its own two action plan for combating bacterial resistance to antimicrobial substances, approved in 2016. This document is not publicly available, though there are references to it e.g. in the [Hygiene Institute reports](#).

III. Chemical threats

a. Key actors and stakeholder networks

The [Ministry of Health](#) in Lithuania is responsible for developing and enforcing health regulations and policies, particularly concerning permissible levels of chemicals in consumer products, food, water and the environment. Through the NPHC, it monitors hazardous chemicals, assesses health risks, and ensures public health protection through emergency preparedness and response plans. Additionally, the Ministry raises public awareness about chemical risks via educational programs and collaborates with national and international bodies to align with global standards.

The [National Public Health Centre \(NPHC\)](#), under the Ministry of Health, controls and assesses chemical-related health risks, environmental, residential and public safety, promotes public awareness, and coordinates responses to chemical incidents with a particular emphasis on identifying and mitigating potential poisoning risks. Safety control and management of chemical events fall within their responsibilities. In the case of chemical pollution, the NPHC orders laboratory tests to the NPHSL to analyse the quality of indoor air in residential and public areas. To assess the extent of chemical contamination, the NPHC evaluates the laboratory test reports and provides recommendations to victims and the public on how to ensure public health safety. It provides the Ministry of Health, the National Crisis Management Centre and the Health Emergency Centre with an annual summary of chemical outbreaks. Control and consultation services are provided to various entities such as dangerous objects (oil storages and refineries, fertiliser storages, thermal boiler houses, explosives warehouse, shooting ranges), prisons, educational institutions, healthcare centres, hospitals and more. Dangerous objects inspections focus on assessing the presence of poisonous substances, storage procedures, the establishment of protection zones, and the inclusion of recommendations in incident management plans. Recommendations are formulated not only for the facilities themselves but also for the benefit of individuals and municipalities. Through the website and social media platforms such as Facebook and LinkedIn, the NPHC actively disseminates information and engages with stakeholders involved in public health and safety.

The [National Public Health Surveillance Laboratory \(NPHSL\)](#) serves as the central institution responsible for detecting chemical hazards that pose risks to public health and carrying out laboratory sampling from the environment in public and residential air. The NPHSL conducts comprehensive chemical analysis and toxicological assessments, providing data to mitigate the impact of chemical incidents. Through its advanced laboratory capabilities and collaboration with other national and international bodies, the NPHSL ensures timely identification and effective management of chemical threats.

The [National Crisis Management Centre \(NCMC\)](#) under the Government of Lithuania is responsible for the management of national-level crises and emergencies. The Center includes a situation center that operates 24/7, continuously monitoring threats to national security. Its primary responsibilities include coordinating with relevant stakeholders during crises, supporting prevention of threats, and overseeing communication related to national security.

The [Fire and Rescue Department](#) under the Ministry of the Interior is the primary stakeholder responsible for emergency response, including chemical threats, dealing directly with emergencies on the field. It operates through a network of regional fire and rescue stations,

ensuring rapid response to incidents across Lithuania. It also engages in public education and awareness campaigns to enhance community preparedness for emergencies.

The [Health Emergency Situations Center \(HESC\)](#) is responsible for ensuring that healthcare establishments are adequately prepared to handle chemical emergencies. This includes overseeing the availability and readiness of necessary medical countermeasures and equipment, although their primary focus tends to be on biological rather than chemical agents. HESC works in coordination with other relevant agencies, including the NPHSL and the Fire and Rescue Department, to ensure an integrated response to chemical incidents. They conduct risk assessments, develop response plans, and ensure that healthcare facilities are compliant with national guidelines for chemical threat preparedness.

The oversight of chemicals entering and being produced in the country is primarily the responsibility of the [Environmental Protection Department](#), under the Ministry of Environment, while the Environmental Protection Agency plays a regulatory role.

The [Lithuanian Environmental Protection Agency](#) oversees and supports environmental monitoring, risk assessment and response coordination. Alongside its broader responsibilities in pollution prevention and conservation, it actively monitors air, water, and soil quality to detect hazardous chemicals and pollutants, assessing their potential impact on human health and the environment. In times of chemical emergencies such as spills or leaks, it supports coordination response efforts, collaborating with various government agencies, emergency responders and industry stakeholders to mitigate risks and protect public health and the environment. Additionally, it enforces environmental regulations related to chemical management and ensures that businesses comply with legal requirements to minimize chemical risks and prevent environmental harm.

In the event of poisoning incidents, such as a parent seeking assistance due to a child ingesting harmful substances, the Poisoning Bureau under the [State Medicines Control Agency \(SMCA\)](#) is the responsible authority. The NPHC handles cases involving significant poisoning incidents.

Other key stakeholders include:

- Municipal health centers
- Public health bureaus
- Municipalities
- State food and veterinary service (including regional branches)

Regarding international collaboration, regular meetings among various stakeholders are held, but due to the limited number of chemical events, there is often not a substantial amount of content to discuss.

b. Digital infrastructures and systems

i. Data sources and systems

The Fire and Rescue Department, as mandated by the government, manages the [Public Warning and Information System \(Gyventoju perspėjimo ir informavimo sistema - GPIS\)](#) in Lithuania. This system requires the six telecommunication providers to enable the dissemination of alarm messages to their users in case of emergencies. The NPHC can utilize this system to send public health-related messages when necessary. All messages are pre-prepared, and the responsible agency assesses the risk and determines the appropriate

message to send based on the nature of the threat. The Fire and Rescue Department oversees and coordinates this system, ensuring that specific threats, such as chemical incidents, are communicated effectively to the public.

Depending on the volume and type of chemicals they handle, companies are required to register their substances with the Environmental Protection Department or the [European Chemicals Agency \(ECHA\)](#) under the [Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals \(REACH\)](#) regulation which facilitates oversight and regulation of hazardous substances.

Each year, the Fire and Rescue Department prepares a plan that includes risk evaluation criteria to determine the number of inspections required. Based on these criteria, a sample of approximately 30 establishments is selected for inspection. These establishments are chosen based on their level of risk, and these criteria are evaluated regularly on a yearly basis. The Fire and Rescue Department is then leading inspections on-site at various establishments, while the NPHC contributes as part of an organized team. While the NPHC provides guidance during inspections, the responsibility for drafting reports and enforcing necessary changes lies with the Fire and Rescue Department. Compliance with regulations is legally mandated for companies, with fines being a potential consequence for failure to adhere to the established requirements. Prior to inspections, the NPHC receives paper-based documentation from companies outlining the necessary requirements for different establishments. Presently, an information system for managing these tasks at the NPHC is lacking. Nevertheless, there are ongoing plans to develop a dedicated system, which will be integrated into the broader public health safety information system. Although the NPHC does not have access to the Fire and Rescue Department system.

The [Substances of Concern In articles as such or in complex objects \(Products\) \(SCIP\)](#) database, was developed by the ECHA and can be consulted by everyone since 24 September 2021. It is a centralized platform for sharing information on hazardous substances in articles and complex products, it aids in compliance monitoring and enhances transparency in the supply chain.

ii. [Data linkage and sharing](#)

The NPHC maintains robust communication protocols with the Ministry to ensure effective information exchange regarding all activities. This includes regular email reporting, by a dedicated mailbox for streamlined communication. Additionally, the NPHC collaborates closely with a communication specialist from the NCMC, utilizing the signal program for secure message sharing. This partnership focuses on writing clear messages for the public to prevent undue alarm and ensure coherent dissemination of information. The coordination process is managed meticulously, with the specialist on duty always able to contact the director or other relevant personnel via phone or email for discussions as needed. While there are no scheduled meetings, this ad hoc communication approach ensures responsiveness and efficiency in addressing any emergent issues.

Regarding chemicals, the NPHC does not routinely send data to international organizations. However, when mandated, they forward information to HESC, which then disseminates it to other countries or the WHO. One significant challenge they face is the absence of clear guidelines regarding when to notify about a chemical threat and what constitutes a serious

incident. In such cases, they adhere to national guidelines established by the government under the State Emergency Management Plan, which provides indicators such as the number of casualties to determine the severity of an event. In instances where a chemical event occurs near the border, they rely on the EWRS to inform neighbouring countries. However, existing European regulations lack specificity, stating that notification is required if the threat is deemed serious and affects another country, but no criteria are specified on how to define a threat as serious.

Depending on the source of the chemical, different stakeholders are responsible for initiating and managing the notification process. The information is then inputted into the EWRS for dissemination and coordination.

iii. Standards and data quality

The country adheres to the standardised terminology from ECHA, often referred to as the "ECHA terminology". ECHA develops and maintains standardized terminology to ensure consistency and clarity in communication related to chemicals and their regulatory processes within the European Union.

iv. Reports

Biweekly meetings are held with all other departments within the NPHC to ensure awareness of their ongoing work, facilitate collaboration and to advocate for initiatives such as the One Health approach. Following coordination efforts among the different departments, an annual report is compiled detailing activities in response to chemical events, including event summaries, recommendations and laboratory testing outcomes, which is then submitted to HESC.

Additionally, there is a quarterly report, primarily for internal use, although there is ongoing discussion regarding its necessity. In recent years, the primary chemical threat has revolved around the damage to mercury-based thermometers. While these reports aim to support preventive measures, measures to mitigate this threat are already established. The municipality allocates funds from public health resources to support these initiatives, specifically targeting efforts to dissuade the purchase of mercury thermometers, which are illegal and typically only available in markets. Collaborative educational activities with health bureaus are being organized to raise awareness and encourage compliance with these regulations.

Annually, the NPHC conducts an evaluation of the emergency plan in collaboration with the HESC. During these evaluations, the plans are reviewed to identify areas for improvement. Continual review and enhancement of these plans are prioritized to ensure preparedness for potential incidents.

v. Medical countermeasures

Responsibility for medical countermeasures against chemical threats, including essential equipment, lies within each organisation for their own personnel. The HESC oversees healthcare establishments, ensuring adequacy of equipment. The Ministry of Health issues public orders outlining the necessary equipment for various scenarios, including CBRN threats. Nonetheless, these directives lack the detailed technical specifications present in guidelines

from other countries, such as the British nomenclature from Information Commissioner's Office (ICO codes). This introduces a risk, as the appropriateness of purchases relies on the expertise of the hospitals' specialists in identifying suitable materials. Hence, there exists potential to bolster these guidelines, given the continual consolidation and updating of current legislation. Ongoing discussions address the necessity of incorporating detailed specifications as the current approach where each institution is defining their own equipment requirements highlights the importance of standardized guidelines to ensure consistency and quality across all procurement activities.

vi. Threat indicators

The response to chemical events involves numerous parallel processes. However, there are no specific thresholds sets that trigger an alarm. Human judgment remains essential due to the nuanced nature of decision-making that requires the use of contextual details. Efforts are underway to standardize such processes and decisions. The NPHSL is engaged in projects focusing on biomonitoring and CBR threats. These initiatives may yield standardized procedures, though it is too early to predict the outcomes.

According to the chemical events, recommendations are provided on appropriate behaviours during accidents, prevention strategies, and methods to minimize health impacts when such events occur. Expert involvement, sourced from either the NPHC or the municipality, is integral to addressing these situations. The Fire and Rescue Department plays a central role in this process. Calls are received round the clock in the event of an emergency, with a dedicated 24/7 hotline in place. Collaboration occurs with the prevention and preparedness office at the municipal level. Following the resolution of an incident, laboratory testing is arranged in residential or public facilities. Subsequently, reports are compiled, outlining guidelines tailored to specific groups, such as advising kindergartens on whether to occupy a particular space and when it is safe to return to the environment.

c. Legislation and strategy

Potential health threats related to chemicals and their monitoring are organised according to:

- [State Emergency Situation Management Plan \(No. 1503\)](#): The law establishes procedures for exchanging information about events, emergencies, or critical situations and providing data on the consequences of such situations including chemical events. It details the responsibilities of various institutions in reporting and managing emergency data, the format and process for information exchange, and the necessary documentation and reporting requirements to ensure coordinated emergency response and management.
- [Law on Environmental Protection \(No. I-2223\)](#): This law establishes the legal framework for environmental protection in Lithuania. It covers the management of natural resources, pollution control, and the responsibilities of state institutions and citizens. Specific articles deal with the production and use of hazardous chemicals and radioactive materials.
- [Law on Chemical Substances and Chemical Mixtures \(No. VIII-1641\)](#): This law, recently amended, provides comprehensive regulation on the management of chemicals, including the classification, labelling and packaging of chemical substances

and mixtures. It aims to protect human health and the environment from the risks posed by chemicals.

The [REACH Regulation](#) governs the safe use of chemicals within the European Union. It imposes obligations on companies to register and report information about the properties and use of chemical substances.

i. Training

The NPHC Vilnius regional department, particularly its product evaluation division, plays an active role in organizing events and educational activities aimed at promoting safe chemical usage. These initiatives include educational events focusing on topics such as the safe handling of chemicals. Additionally, the NPHC coordinates lectures at schools, addressing chemical safety issues directly with students. These educational activities encompass learning on how to identify different chemicals and understanding their potential risks.

The NPHC is participating in initiatives like the European Gateway Project that stands for sustainable and trusted connections that work for people and the planet. It helps to tackle the most pressing global challenges, from fighting climate change, to improving health systems, and boosting competitiveness and security of global supply chains. Recognizing the importance of continuous education and professional development, the NPHC is currently preparing a proposal to enhance specialists' education. This proposal aims to leverage materials prepared through the project, ensuring that specialists are equipped with the latest knowledge and skills to address emerging challenges effectively.

IV. Nuclear & Radiological threats

Lithuania currently does not have any operating Nuclear Power Plants (NPP) on its territory, as the Ignalina NPP is undergoing decommissioning. The decommissioning process began in 2010 and is expected to be completed by 2038. However, its neighbouring countries, such as Belarus and Russia, have constructed or had plans to construct NPP relatively close to Lithuania's borders.

- Belarus constructed the Astravyets NPP on the Lithuanian border, approximately 50 kilometers away from Vilnius, the capital of Lithuania. The construction of this plant has raised concerns in Lithuania regarding safety and environmental risks.
- Russia planned to build a NPP in the Kaliningrad Oblast, a Russian exclave located between Poland and Lithuania on the Baltic. During the construction phase, this plan raised concerns for Lithuania however, the construction works started in 2008 and halted in 2013.

Specific bilateral agreements exist with Belarus regarding radiological and nuclear emergencies and diplomatic relations with Belarus are maintained. However, concerns persist regarding timely information sharing during emergencies, prompting Lithuania to prepare for various scenarios. Both countries are members of [International Atomic Energy Agency \(IAEA\)](#), that supports mutual information exchange through the controlling agency.

Collaborative handling of threats between Lithuania and Belarus is unlikely due to differing preparedness zones. Lithuania opts for larger zones compared to Belarus, as dictated by IAEA guidelines. For instance, precautionary action zones range from 15 to 30 km: Belarus selects 15 km while Lithuania selects 30 km.

Additionally, a physical barrier has been erected on the border due to hybrid threats originating from Belarus, notably the influx of migrants from Russia. This barrier serves as a component of crisis management for technogenic emergencies, such as those involving NPP which may also serve as a deterrent against hybrid threats (situations where emergencies or incidents could be exploited for military escalation into the country). However, it is recognized that relying solely on this barrier may not provide sufficient protection in the face of such complex threats.

a. Key actors and stakeholder networks

The [Radiation Protection Center \(RPC\)](#) is the regulatory authority for radiation protection, responsible for implementing regulatory control over public and environmental exposure, as well as the use of sources of ionizing radiation - except for practices within the nuclear energy field. It also participates in the formulation of the state policy on radiation protection, as entrusted by the Minister of Health, and is responsible for early warning, assessing radiation risks and providing recommendations on protective measures to minimize exposure to radiation. It plays a crucial role in assessing the extent of contamination and informing the public and first responders about potential health risks. The work encompasses licensing, transportation, inspections and all aspects related to radiological sources and protection. Within the Center, trainings are also organised for all individuals handling radiological materials, including first responders.

The institution responsible for the oversight and regulation of nuclear installations is the [State Nuclear Power Safety Inspectorate \(VATESI\)](#). VATESI is tasked with ensuring the safety of

nuclear activities, including the decommissioning of NPP, the supervision of safety construction and operation of radioactive waste management facilities and the enforcement of nuclear safety regulations. They ensure compliance with safety standards and respond to any safety or security incidents at nuclear facilities.

The [Ministry of Health](#) oversees the public health aspects of radiological and nuclear threats management. It ensures medical preparedness, provides guidelines for radiation protection and coordinates healthcare responses during radiological emergencies.

The [National Crisis Management Centre \(NCMC\)](#) under the Government of Lithuania is responsible for the management of national-level crises and emergencies. The Center includes a situation center that operates 24/7, continuously monitoring threats to national security. Its primary responsibilities include coordinating with relevant stakeholders during crises, supporting prevention of threats and overseeing communication related to national security.

The [Fire and Rescue Department](#) under the Ministry of the Interior is the primary stakeholder responsible for emergency response, including nuclear threats, dealing directly with emergencies on the field. It operates through a network of regional fire and rescue stations, ensuring rapid response to incidents across Lithuania. It also engages in public education and awareness campaigns to enhance community preparedness for emergencies.

Other key stakeholders in the management of radiological and nuclear threats include:

- Ministry of Interior
- State Border Guard Service
- State food and veterinary service
- Municipalities
- Customs of the Republic of Lithuania

The duties and responsibilities of each stakeholder in the case of nuclear or radiological emergency are described in two national plans:

- The [State Emergency Management Plan](#)
- The [State Plan of Public Protection in Case of Nuclear or Radiological Accident](#)

Engagement with international organizations plays a key role in management and preparedness for health emergencies related to nuclear and radiological threats and it includes collaboration with entities such as the European Commission (EC), the IAEA, other national public health agencies and the United Nations conventions, facilitating early notifications and information exchange mechanisms.

b. Digital infrastructures and systems

i. Data sources and systems

In accordance with the Law on Radiation Safety, information related to such threats is gathered via:

- Radiation early warning system (confidential information)
- Radiation protection information system (ionizing radiation sources and monitoring occupational exposure)

RPC manages the **Radiation Early Warning System (RADIS)** in Lithuania, overseeing a network of portal monitors across the country. Responsibility for maintenance and receipt of initial notifications in case of any incidents lies with the Center. There are 44 RADIS stations throughout Lithuania, with a higher concentration near the Belarus NPP and the Belarus border, in readiness for potential events in that area. Additionally, four stations are situated in Neris and Nemunas rivers. Data from these RADIS stations are automatically collected and transmitted to the Center's servers every ten minutes. If elevated radiation levels are detected, the team assesses the threat and provides recommendations accordingly. Data from the RADIS stations are shared with the public through a [dashboard](#). Validation and verification of the data occur before making it available to the public to avoid unnecessary concern caused by false alarms or technical errors at the monitoring stations. Quality data checks are primarily conducted automatically, except when alarm levels are triggered. In such cases, specialists manually review the data to determine if the alarm is genuine or due to an error. They then make decisions regarding whether the alarm is false or valid, and whether additional measurements or actions are necessary to confirm its accuracy.

Lithuania also has a system for managing [ionizing radiation sources and monitoring occupational exposure](#). This system, overseen by the RPC, includes a detailed state register that tracks all sources of ionizing radiation, such as X-ray machines and radioactive materials. It records radiation exposure levels of workers who work with these sources, ensuring their health and safety. To improve data management, servers hosting dosimetry information are gradually being moved to the [national cloud](#). The additional updates to this system aim to enhance its digital capabilities by increasing direct data input and reducing paperwork, thus streamlining procedures and improving efficiency. These efforts are part of national projects and include a collaboration with the IAEA to further enhance regulatory practices on a regional scale.

The [Environmental Protection Agency](#) operates additional stations dedicated to routine monitoring of groundwater and air quality. Ad hoc monitoring activities are conducted by the NPHSL. The Minister of Energy's strategic plan for 2050 aligns with these initiatives, anticipating the potential deployment of small modular reactors even in major cities, although specifics remain tentative at this stage.

Data collection at designated points of entry (defined in the [State Border and its Protection of the Republic of Lithuania Nr. VIII-1666](#)) occurs at three international airports and one seaport, referred to as radiation gates which are at borders with third countries. These gates measure individuals and vehicles, and the data collected is managed by border guard services using a local system. When an alarm is triggered, notifications are sent to the relevant stakeholders with the detected measurements and the threat is evaluated by experts. For specific cases, such as a person triggering the radiation detection systems due to their consumption of iodine (used in medical treatments for e.g. thyroid conditions), border guards verify medical documentation and decide if further action is necessary. For more complex cases, border guards contact the 24/7 support service from the RPC for advice before making decisions. This process involves initial phone calls and additional documentation in paper form if needed. There are no current plans to further digitalize this procedure, as the existing system is clear, infrequently used and effective for both monitoring individuals and cargo.

No work on AI is currently planned. The manufacturer of the existing early warning systems is developing AI capabilities for these systems, but such AI-enhanced stations are not yet available for purchase as they are still in development.

ii. Data sharing

For exchanging information internationally, the country uses the [Unified System for Information Exchange in Incidents and Emergencies \(USIE\)](#), a secure website maintained by the IAEA to enable countries to exchange urgent notifications and follow-up information during an emergency. This system is designed for international information exchange, enabling the finding and dissemination of information. According to legislation, any alarm from these systems is immediately relayed to the relevant authorities. Conversely, if an alarm occurs within the country, the information is provided to the regulator to be entered into the system.

RADIS data is shared with [European Radiological Data Exchange Platform \(EURDEP\)](#) for broader European monitoring. To share data with the platform, specific standards for harmonization must be followed. This transmission occurs automatically, either through data extraction directly from the Center's servers or by exporting files in a specified format for communication with the platform.

Lithuania also shares information about radiological incidents and emergencies with the [Incident and Trafficking Database \(ITDB\)](#) maintained by the IAEA. This database is a central repository for information related to incidents involving the unauthorized possession, theft, loss, or unauthorized use of nuclear and other radioactive material. The purpose of ITDB is to help member states of the IAEA share information and collaborate to prevent, detect, and respond to illicit trafficking and other unauthorized activities involving nuclear materials.

Visits to other countries to gain insight into their operations are regularly organised. Numerous projects working groups and workshops take place annually on early warning, inspections, medicine, public exposures and emergencies. These meetings provide opportunities for sharing experiences with other nations, with some countries also visiting Lithuanian's facilities to gain experience from RPC specialists. This dynamic fosters a continuous exchange of knowledge and experience among participating countries.

iii. Standards and data quality

The RPC, in collaboration with the Border Guard Service, has developed and approved standardized notification forms. These forms serve as essential tools for promptly reporting incidents or emergencies involving ionizing radiation across borders or within the country. They ensure a consistent and efficient communication process between relevant authorities, facilitating timely response measures. Similarly, HESC and the Fire and Rescue Department have also established approved notification forms tailored specifically for reporting national-level emergencies related to radiation or other health and safety concerns. These standardized forms enable swift and coordinated responses from emergency services and governmental agencies, ensuring effective management of crises and safeguarding public health and safety.

iv. Reports

Every year, an institutional report is prepared, summarizing the activities and achievements of the previous year. This comprehensive report covers all topics and activities, including a section on nuclear or radiological emergency preparedness detailing the training conducted and the current situation in the country. These reports are produced in both Lithuanian and English and are published on the [institutes' website](#) annually.

Multiple exercises, including national exercises for nuclear emergency, are held at least annually since 2019, and sometimes more frequently. Additionally, other types of exercises, such as institutional or municipal level field or table exercises, are organised. Regardless of the exercise level and type (national, institutional, municipal, field, or tabletop), a report is produced. This report assesses all activities, identifies areas for improvement and sets deadlines for addressing any issues discovered.

v. Medical countermeasures

Regarding medical countermeasures, the stockpile system is organized into three tiers: institution level, municipality, and state reserve. Recommendations are provided on the materials and equipment necessary for safety, including product identification and specific quantities, such as types of PPE, duration of stay in certain areas and instructions on behaviours to follow.

For healthcare institutions, [Order Nr. V-2225](#) sets forth clear directives regarding the amounts of medical supplies and PPE they must maintain in their inventories.

The stockpile system's development and management involve extensive collaboration and coordination among relevant authorities and HESC. HESC conducts regular checks and assessments to verify healthcare institutions' compliance with the established requirements. These verification checks are conducted through data collection methods rather than direct inspections, due to the logistical challenges of physically counting the extensive inventory of materials.

vi. Threat indicators

Nuclear or radiological health threats are identified through:

- Event-based
- Indicator(s)-based
- Threshold

A team of five to seven specialists monitors the RADIS system continuously, 24/7. The RADIS system is designed to automatically detect anomalies or instances where values surpass predefined thresholds. There are currently 44 stations for environmental monitoring and four for water monitoring. There are automatic radiation detection systems (radiation gates) at border crossing points, which automatically detect the presence of ionising radiation.

First responders, the Border Guard Services, Customs of the Republic of Lithuania and hospitals also have handheld devices which allows to detect presence of ionizing radiation manually. According to The Rules on The Handling of Orphan Ionizing Radiation Sources, Substances of Orphan Nuclear Fuel Cycle, Orphan Nuclear and Fissile Substances and Objects Contaminated by Radionuclides, if detected radiation level at Point of Entry exceed 0.1 mSv/h (millisievert per hour), the Border Guard Service must immediately inform RPC and coordinate follow-up actions.

When RADIS stations detect radiation level above 300 mSv/h, the responsible RPC specialist verifies the data and, if confirmed as real threat, RPC initiates the activation of the State Plan of Public Protection in Case of Nuclear or Radiological Accident. In cases requiring intervention, a response team is mobilized, the composition of which is defined depending on

the nature of the threat. The appropriate personnel are promptly informed, activating the contacts with HESC to notify the government and other relevant institutions, ensuring coordinated response efforts.

The State Emergency Management Plan addresses 16 types of emergencies, including radiological emergencies, specifying the responsible and supportive institutions and their functions. There is a clear division of functions and responsibilities, along with an algorithm for information exchange. Public communication during such emergencies is handled by the government.

Regarding communication to the public, [LT72](#) is a website intended to prepare Lithuanian residents for emergencies. It allows residents to learn how to be prepared for an accident, how to behave in the event of an emergency, how to receive the information needed during emergencies and other threats.

c. Legislation and strategy

Potential health threats related to the effects of ionising radiation are detected according to:

- [Radiation Safety Law No. VIII-1019](#)
- [The State Emergency Management Plan](#)
- [The State Plan of Public Protection in Case of Nuclear or Radiological Accident](#)
- [The Rules on The Handling of Orphan Ionizing Radiation Sources, Substances of Orphan Nuclear Fuel Cycle, Orphan Nuclear and Fissile Substances and Objects Contaminated by Radionuclides](#)
- [Description of the Information Exchange Procedure in Case of an Imminent or Actual Nuclear or Radiological Accident](#)

These documents also specify how information should be shared among the relevant stakeholders. Clear algorithms specify the procedures for communication, including who initiates contact, the timing, the relevant contact numbers and the required information. The national regulatory framework is updated according to latest published international recommendations.

In accordance with the inter-governmental agreements with Denmark, Norway, Latvia, Poland and Belarus, Lithuania is obligated to provide information about nuclear events in the country. Key legislatures and tools that define international notification about nuclear or radiological emergency are:

- Decree on Acceptance to the [1986 Convention Early Notification of a Nuclear Accident](#)
- [Convention on Early Notification of a Nuclear Accident](#)
- [Convention on Assistance in the Case of a Nuclear Accident or Radiological Emergency](#)

Regarding cooperation with international organisations, the main stakeholders include:

- The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA);
- World Health Organisation (WHO);
- European Commission (EC);
- The European Nuclear Safety Regulators Group (ENSREG);
- The Western European Nuclear Regulators Association (WENRA);
- Heads of the European Radiological Protection Competent Authorities (HERCA)

- The European Nuclear Security Regulators Association (ENSRA);
- European Safeguards Research and Development Association (ESARDA);
- European Network on Operating Experience Feedback.

i. Preparedness plans

In the State Plan of Public Protection in Case of Nuclear or Radiological Accident, five hospitals are designated for handling patients exposed to ionizing radiation. RPC provides training to hospitals' staff on radiation protection measures, contamination management, physical protection, decontamination procedures and patient measurements. Trainings are available to all Lithuanian hospitals, but the main focus is for hospitals within 100 km of Belarus NPP. RPC also provides training to first responders and anyone interested in responding to radiological or nuclear emergencies.

Hospitals are not always required to have a separate plan specifically for radiological emergencies however, they must have a general emergency situation management plan. During the preparation of this plan, a risk assessment is conducted according to the Fire and Rescue Department approved methodology. If the risk assessment indicates that the radiological or nuclear threat is very high or high, the plan must include a detailed description of the actions to be taken in such emergencies. These plans are reviewed by HESC.

Internal institutional emergency management plans are reviewed annually. The national emergency management plan is currently undergoing revision, with updates made as needed in response to regulatory changes. For instance, revisions are prompted by updates to national law on civil protection, which was enacted by parliament in December 2022 but activated from January 1st of the following year. The ongoing updates to the emergency plans reflect the evolving legislative landscape, although the exact progress of these revisions may vary.

In Lithuania, no universities offer programs specifically for training radiation protection specialists. There are related programs for medical physicists who work with medical devices using radiation sources. However, radiation protection specialists are primarily trained by international organisations and other institutions through workshops, training sessions and specialized schools.

V. Medical countermeasures

a. Key actors and stakeholder networks

The National Crises Management Center under the Government of the Republic of Lithuania was established in 2022¹ with the task to structurally review the composition of the entire state reserve and eliminate possible duplications between food, civil defense, medical supplies and other reserves. The state reserve covering pandemic, nuclear and war situations is managed by different ministries according to their respective jurisdiction. Each ministry that manages their respective part of the state reserve decides what should be included.

The [Ministry of Health](#) conducts a threat assessment of the medical system in crisis situations every two years and all medical reserves are based on this analysis. Review of the medical stockpiles (items and quantities) is conducted in light of changes of threats, and HESC changes the stocks accordingly. The country has more than 50 years practice in medical reserves stockpiling. Specific information of the medical countermeasures and stocks is classified.

[HESC](#) under the Ministry of Health is responsible for administering the state reserve of MCM. Its Medical Reserve Planning Department is responsible for planning the stocks and managing procurement procedures as well as the sale and/or donation of goods from the stock, and the Medicine Reserve Storage and Pharmaceutical Activity Department is responsible for the state reserve storing, distributing, and quality assurance. The Department is responsible for four warehouses in two locations across the country. The Government of the Republic of Lithuania annually forms and assigns MCM accumulation and renewal tasks to HESC and the necessary funding for this purpose - for MCM purchase and for covering all storage and administration costs.

In medical stockpiling, HESC is working with the [National Public Health Center](#) and [State Medicines Control Agency](#) both through informal connections and formal working groups related to e.g. vaccine distribution and vaccine related questions (both COVID-19 specific and broader). These working groups are established by ministerial orders and their membership includes representatives also from hospitals, research/scientists and the Ministry of Health.

[Ministry of the Interior](#) has an overall coordination role for civil protection. One of the key actors in the civil safety and rescue system, the Department of Fire Protection and Rescue is managed by the Ministry of the Interior.

With regards to the transportation of supplies during emergencies, there is ongoing discussion on the role of the [Ministry of Transport and Communications](#). The Ministry was responsible for transportation of emergency donations to Ukraine, including medical stocks, in the beginning of Russia's war of aggression in Ukraine in 2022.

¹ <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/044f60e1875e11edbdcebd68a7a0df7e/asr>

Figure 1. Civil protection and crisis management system in Lithuania.

Source: HESC

Relevant international collaboration in MCM related matters includes firstly participation in [rescEU](#), the European Union (EU) reserve of European capacities to protect citizens from disasters and manage emerging risks. Lithuania is one of the countries for which the EU has allocated funding to further develop the rescEU strategic reserves of medical and chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear (CBRN) items. For the country this implies the need to acquire additional warehouses. HESC is responsible for establishing and maintaining the warehouses in collaboration with the Ministries of Interior and Transport. Main challenge identified for rescEU is the risk of hybrid attacks to the warehouses. Moreover, the sustainability of the initiative, i.e. what happens with the warehouses after the 3-year initiative, has not been discussed according to HESC. HESC is looking for new warehouses in safer places than the current warehouses, the location of which is not disclosed.

Lithuania is also participating in the [EU Joint Action on Coordination and Harmonisation of the Existing Systems against Shortages of Medicines – European Network \(CHESSMEN\)](#) aiming to mitigate medicine shortages.

Furthermore, HESC has been part of the information collection by the Health Information and Quality Authority of Ireland with the aim to develop a national stockpiling strategy for Ireland.

b. Digital infrastructures and systems

The national stockpile system in Lithuania is multi-layered. The first layer requires all hospitals and healthcare institutions to maintain a one-month supply of personal protective equipment (PPE) and other essential equipment. The second layer involves municipalities, which must have stockpiles for their needs and those of local institutions. The final layer is the HESC medical stockpile. The state reserve can be used only by government decision in a serious emergency situation. HESC is responsible for distributing the supplies to the hospitals in emergencies. This entire system is now part of the updated pandemic preparedness plan.

The latest review of the content of the medical reserves was conducted in 2022-23 by a working group of experts established by the Minister of Health and including experts from

medical institutions, army, and the Ministry of Health including HESC. The group analysed all threats and all needs of medical institutions and recommended changes that were implemented in 2023. Next, HESC will review the PPE set in order to reduce the amount of MCM. As one basis for assessing the size of the stock, the country uses the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) traffic light method to assess all medical equipment and medical counter measures.

At the national level, bottlenecks in the supply chains for MCMs include shortages in the production or availability of specific medicines required for the national reserve, as well as challenges in procuring medicines with more than 75% of their shelf life remaining, which is necessary for efficient stock rotation. Additionally, the organization of the transportation for distribution of medical stocks has been identified as a challenge by HESC as the center does not have a transportation service. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the healthcare institutions had to rely on their respective transportation services to collect the vaccines from HESC. This posed a challenge for ensuring functioning cold chain and meeting other requirements for the transportation of the vaccines. In the short term, this was solved by HESC receiving additional funding and acquiring transportation services for vaccines through public procurement. However, organizing the distribution of MCM in the event of other types of health emergencies will be complex with possible support from the military and from the Fire and Rescue Department. However, to address the issue of scaling up transportation capacity in emergencies, one suggested solution is that the Ministry of Transport and Communications be responsible for all transportation in emergencies. This is one area of work in which information exchange via the rescEU project could be beneficial.

i. Data sources and systems

There is no overall national stockpiling system with a central management system. MCM, as part of state medical reserve (state medical stockpile), are managed by HESC using an inventory accounting information system. Since the end of 2023, HESC is implementing a new **warehouse information management system**, namely the warehouse management module of "[SCExpert](#)". Data transfer from the old system to the new one is ongoing and scheduled to be completed in the end of April 2024. Although the data has been transferred, minor inaccuracies in the data remain and therefore, the implementation plan has been extended to April 2025. Records on stocks, their quantities, cost, production, and expiry dates of these MCM as well as stock movements are kept in this system. Based on the data on stock quantity and expiry dates, public procurements and stock renewal needs are planned. The system is not interoperable with any other public health information system (eHealth, e-prescription) due to the restricted nature of the national stockpiling information and its use is restricted to HESC staff members on a need-to-know basis. No other organisation, e.g. the Ministry of Health, can have access to the system.

Funding for the new system was provided by the Government. There is a common budget for all aspects of state reserve and its administration that are covered by different ministries. The old system did not entail warehouse location mapping which is a significant improvement in the new system. With the new system, warehouse information management is modernized, and most processes digitized, reducing paperwork and e.g. manual calculation of the quantities of medicines. Further improvements in the digitalization of stock management include the planned introduction of scanners at the entry to the warehouse submitting information directly to the warehouse information system and measuring the stock quantities.

For the warehouse information management system data is collected from the warehouses. There is no automatic data quality check, but data quality control takes place manually. Inventories of the stocks takes place in regular intervals: medicine inventory every quarter, hospital supplies set every two quarters, and an annual inventory for accounting data. There is no automatic trigger in the warehouse management system to alert low level of stocks. The information about the target amount of stockpiles is stored in a different place and comparison with the existing volume of stocks is conducted by the Medical Reserve Planning Department.

In the stock management process of HESC, a review of all the medical stocks takes place quarterly and rotation of the stocks is conducted halfway through the shelf life and procedure exists for selling the stocks approaching the end of the shelf life (only stocks with shelf life shorter than seven months). Medicines are sold only to the institutions with licenses to get medication i.e. hospitals and pharmacies, whereas PPE may be sold to any actor. Unsold goods may be also donated to the hospitals.

HESC receives information from stockpiles in healthcare institutions ESVIS. The overall status of the national medical stockpiles is thus consolidated from the two systems. There is no operational and united information system in place that would also cover the municipalities. Municipalities would report quarterly on their reserves but this not obligatory.

Regarding the second system for MCM in the country, ESVIS was first used during the COVID-19 pandemic to procure and distribute vaccinations as well as to manage COVID-19 test appointments. Currently two new modules are under development:

- A pilot project to add a new module to the system to organise and book state-financed transportation services to the nearest active hospital for patients requiring inpatient treatment, especially with low socio-economic status, disease or disabilities. Due to a declining population, past and present governments have decided to reduce the number of active care facilities and provide state-funded transportation for patients needing inpatient care. Currently, this service is being tested in pilot regions like Kaunas and Penevėžys.
- Preparedness and prevention monitoring and management: this module contains information about all the healthcare institutions' preparedness plans including their staff, responsible people and the medical countermeasures. This implies digitalization of the plans that are thus far paper-based.

HESC will continue to develop ESVIS to create an information system for hospitals and healthcare institutions providing real-time data on resources. Additional functionalities also include automatization of notifications of CBRN especially of international concern. Furthermore, HESC is reviewing the PPE set to reduce the quantities, taking into account the existing PPE reserves in the medical institutions. The goal is to connect this system with the EU Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority information technology (IT) platform for better preparedness across Europe. Lithuania also uses various information systems connected with ECDC, TESSy, and the EU Civil Protection Mechanism for emergency situations and patient transportation. Information about MCM is not shared as the information on the national reserves would fall into the category of sensitive/nondisclosed information and data on the institutional reserves are not updated on daily nor weekly basis.

ii. Data storage

The first and second level owners of national medical stockpiles - hospitals and municipalities – have their own information management systems in place. However, HESC has an electronic system through which hospitals or entities can order vaccines. This information is reviewed weekly in Excel format and submitted to the HESC transportation service company responsible for distribution.

For the warehouse information system as well as the ESVIS system, HESC is responsible for safe connection. HESC internal systems are operational and set according to the national cybersecurity standards set by [The Core Center of State Telecommunications](#). The institutional policies (including the external systems i.a. ESVIS) on management of IT systems must be submitted to this centre for approval. Moreover, from 2023 onwards HESC provides the web services through the national secure network "Saugusis valstybinis duomenų perdavimo tinklas (toliau – SVDPT)".

iii. Data linkage and sharing

The data in the HESC warehouse information system is not shared. Data sharing regarding national MCM stockpiles with the Ministry of Health is paper-based and classified.

Regarding the rescEU project impact on IT system, the rescEU, stocks will be stored in rented warehouses. The public procurement specification will take into account the warehouse information needs – how to transfer the data from the rented warehouses to HESC warehouse information system, or alternatively grant HESC access with some restrictions to the supplier data to monitor the stocks. Whether the data transfer could be done with APIs and its cost implications are still under assessment.

HESC is planning to make some of its data available in the [Lithuanian government open data portal](#) in 2024, namely the availability of iodine, humanitarian aid, and nuclear specific MCM distributed to healthcare institutions.

iv. Reports

HESC reports to the Ministry of Health annually, in November, on the level of the national reserve and the rotation needs. This forms a basis for the budget for the next year. The report is extracted from the warehouse information management system and delivered to the Ministry of Health as classified information. The percentage of existing stocks (vis-à-vis the target amount) is reported to the Ministry of Health on a quarterly basis.

Lithuania does not report MCM-related data internationally. Joint procurement possibility is under discussion with Latvia and Estonia, yet the subject is difficult due to the classified nature of national stockpiles in each country as well as differences in public procurement legislation.

c. Legislation and strategy

The [Crisis Management and Civil Protection Law of the Republic of Lithuania](#) (Law No. VIII-971) in 1998 establishes “*the legal and organizational bases for the organization and operation of the civil protection and rescue system of the Republic of Lithuania, the duties and rights of state and municipal institutions, economic entities, public organizations and residents in the field of civil protection*”.

[The law has been reviewed](#) several times during 2023 and 2024 mainly in relation to its implementation mechanisms. [Resolution No. 31/07/2023 638](#) entails the establishment of National Security Commission and the Joint Threat Prevention and Crisis Management Group. It also “*authorizes the Minister of Health to determine the list and quantities of personal protective equipment and other necessary equipment, medical equipment and biocides to protect against a dangerous or particularly dangerous infectious disease to be accumulated by the entities specified in the List*”; and to “*approve the description of the procedure for determining the list and quantity of medical devices of the entities specified in the List*”. Furthermore it confirms “*the list of state and municipal institutions and institutions, other institutions, economic entities and operators who are required to stockpile the necessary measures and personal protective measures to ensure their continuous operation; and the description of the procedure for determining the list, quantity and period of necessary measures and personal protective measures accumulated by state and municipal institutions and institutions, other institutions, economic entities and operators to ensure the continuous performance of their activities*”. The resolution also confirms “*the criteria with which managers of other institutions and economic entities must organize the preparation of an extreme situation management plan*”.

The [State Reserve Law of the Republic of Lithuania](#) (Law No. VIII–1908) entered into force in 2000, covering “*the establishment, accumulation, management and administration of the Lithuanian state reserve*”. The law has been amended a number of times, the latest amendment dating to June 2024 and covering i.a. changes to the rotation of stocks and additional institutions for which expiring stocks may be donated.

i. Emergency plans

There are various separate regulations for emergency preparedness for the health sector in the country and a process is ongoing to merge them into one ministerial order (consisting of 13 separate parts on every single aspect on preparedness and response), to complement the [Order on the Approval of Recommendations for the Preparation of an Emergency Plan for a Personal Health Care Institution](#) (Order No. V-157, March 2003). With [the new merged regulation on preparedness and planning](#) (Order No. V-937, May 2022), all healthcare institutions are required to develop emergency preparedness plans for which the quality assurance is conducted by HESC.

An emergency plan for HESC exists and it is reviewed and updated according to changes in the national legislation.

Regarding staff and training, HESC is in the process of obtaining WHO certification of emergency medical team command. Additionally, the HESC pharmacists provide annual training on updates on the legislation and regulation and procedures for storing different medical products.

CONCLUSIONS

This report presents the findings of the country visit in Lithuania as part of the EU-HIP project, which aimed to collect additional information on digital systems for surveillance and monitoring of PHPP, AMR, CBRN threats and related MCM. The content of the report reflects the information collected via the initial landscape analysis of the EU-HIP project, as well as the interviews carried out in April 2024.

The purpose of collecting and compiling this country-specific material was to make available, to the national stakeholders and the experts working on building the ATHINA platform, an initial state-of-play of the national IT systems in place for health threats surveillance and to support further work within the EU-HIP project.

For this upcoming work, the identification of key areas of improvement and actions to strive towards interoperability with the ATHINA platform are needed. In this regard, the next phase of the EU-HIP project involves evaluating the national technical needs to strengthen health information systems at the country level (D5.1 Needs Analysis). These enhancements include developing new systems and processes, building upon, complementing or expanding existing systems, further digitising workflows and promote the use of international standards. Additionally, these insights will guide upcoming discussions with HERA regarding the development of ATHINA and the EU-HIP future work.

Additionally, this exercise created opportunities for national stakeholders to connect, interact and gain deeper insights into each other's activities, with great potential to strengthen internal collaboration and identify key areas of improvement.

ANNEX 1

List of dangerous and especially dangerous infectious diseases, for which patients, persons suspected of having dangerous or especially dangerous infectious diseases, persons who have had contact, or carriers of the pathogens of these diseases must be hospitalized and/or isolated, examined and/or treated mandatorily²

Dangerous infectious diseases:

1. Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) disease or carrier state
2. Acute poliomyelitis
3. Measles
4. Rubella
5. Influenza
6. Cytomegalovirus diseases
7. Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease
8. Other chronic viral infections of the central nervous system
9. Infectious mononucleosis
10. Viral hepatitis or carrier state of viral hepatitis B and C
11. Viral intestinal infections
12. Rabies
13. Tick-borne viral encephalitis (Russian spring-summer encephalitis)
14. Haemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome
15. Diphtheria or carrier state
16. Pertussis (whooping cough)
17. Meningococcal infection or carrier state
18. Bacterial meningitis
19. Tuberculosis
20. Leprosy
21. Shigellosis or carrier state
22. Typhoid fever or carrier state
23. Paratyphoid fever or carrier state
24. Other salmonellosis or carrier state
25. Other bacterial intestinal infections
26. Other bacterial foodborne toxic infections
27. Extraintestinal yersiniosis
28. Brucellosis
29. Listeriosis
30. Leptospirosis
31. Foot-and-mouth disease
32. Anthrax
33. Tularaemia
34. Tetanus
35. Streptococcal and other septicemias
36. Gas gangrene
37. Lyme disease

² Translated from Lithuanian to English. Original source available at <https://www.e-tar.lt/portal/en/legalAct/TAR.AC1276247576/zcgPYezxdc>

38. Legionellosis
39. Syphilis
40. Gonococcal infection
41. Ornithosis
42. Psittacosis
43. Other chlamydia-related diseases
44. Other mycoplasma-related diseases
45. Epidemic typhus and Brill's disease
46. Q fever
47. Malaria
48. Amebiasis
49. Balantidiasis
50. Toxoplasmosis
51. Leishmaniasis
52. Trichinellosis
53. Echinococcosis
54. Taeniasis
55. Cysticercosis
56. Toxocariasis
57. Crimean-Congo Haemorrhagic fever
58. Dengue Haemorrhagic fever
59. Rift Valley fever
60. Bolivian Haemorrhagic fever
61. Argentine Haemorrhagic fever
62. Venezuelan equine encephalitis
63. Western equine encephalitis
64. Eastern equine encephalitis
65. Japanese encephalitis
66. California encephalitis
67. St. Louis encephalitis
68. West Nile fever
69. Dermatophytosis (ringworm, microsporia, trichophytia)
70. Deep mycoses
71. Scabies
72. Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS)
73. Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) infection
74. COVID-19 disease (coronavirus infection)

Very Dangerous Infectious Diseases:

1. Plague
2. Cholera or carrier status
3. Monkeypox
4. Yellow fever
5. Viral hemorrhagic fevers:
 - 5.1. Marburg virus disease
 - 5.2. Ebola virus disease
 - 5.3. Lassa fever
6. Smallpox